

Productive tillers/plant, flag leaf area, and yield/plant of Basmati 370 and NIAB Rice-1 in both environments differed significantly (see table). Plant height did not differ. Performance of the F₁s of Basmati 370/NIAB Rice-1 and NIAB Rice-1/Basmati 370 did not

differ. The F₁s showed heterosis over Basmati 370 for all the traits studied. However, true heterobeltiosis was observed only for plant height.

These results indicate the absence of any extragenic basis of salt tolerance, at least for these two genotypes. □

TTB15-1 is 90 cm tall with intermediate tillering ability and 114-125 d duration. It is awnless, medium-grained, with fully exerted panicles. The 1,000-grain weight is 22.0 g. It has nonglutinous endosperm with translucent white kernels and acceptable cooking quality.

TTB15-1 is moderately resistant to bacterial blight, brown planthopper, and whitebacked planthopper but susceptible to blast. It is resistant to shattering.

In eight transplanting trials in Karimganj and Titabar, yield was 8-36.8% higher than that of check varieties (see table). In on-farm trials, its yield advantage was higher because a low yielding local traditional ahu variety was used as the check. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Release of new rice cultivar Jasmine 85 in USA

C. N. Bollich, Agricultural Research Service (ARS), USDA, Route 7, Box 999, Beaumont, Texas 77713, USA

The release of Jasmine 85, a new long-grain rice cultivar, was announced by ARS, U.S. Department of Agriculture and the agricultural experiment stations of Texas, Mississippi, Arkansas, and Louisiana.

Jasmine 85 (IR841) derives from the IRRI cross IR262/Khao Dawk Mali

105. IR262 was from the cross Peta *3/ Taichung Native 1.

Jasmine 85 is an aromatic (scented) rice possessing the flavor and aroma of fragrant rices of Thailand. Average amylose content is 17% and alkali spreading value 6.5. This characterizes Jasmine 85 as a low-amylose, low-gelatinization-temperature type similar to Thai fragrant rices. Typically, cooked grains of Jasmine 85, like those of the Thai fragrant rices, are soft and cohesive with the cooked kernels tending to cling together. □

Medium-duration Taichung Sen Yu 285 released in Sichuan as Chuan Mi 2

Deng Jutao, Luo Wenzhi, Yuan Zuolian, and Yin Guoda, Rice Research Institute (RRI), Sichuan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Luzhou, Sichuan, China

Taichung Sen Yu 285, an International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) entry from Taiwan, evaluated in Sichuan since 1983—at RRI for 3 yr and in regional provincial tests for 2 yr—was released in Mar 1989 as Chuan Mi 2 for cultivation in Sichuan.

Mean grain yield over 3 yr in RRI trials was 7.6 t/ha, 7% higher than the local check (see table). In the 1986-87 regional test for grain quality, mean grain yield was 7.4 t/ha, 6% higher than the local check. In 1988 Adaptive Research Trials in three counties, mean grain yield was 7.4 t/ha, 7% higher than the local check.

Chuan Mi 2 is a semidwarf (90-95 cm), heavy-tillering rice with 135-140 d duration. Grain is medium slender, fine and white, with 3.6% amylose and 10.73% protein content. It has 73% milling recovery and good cooking quality.

TTB15-1, a promising rice variety for Assam

T. Ahmed, R. K. S. M. Barua, K. C. Sarma, G. R. Das, K. K. Sarma, D. K. Barua, U. Kalita, P. K. Pathak, and A. K. Pathak, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Assam Agricultural University, Titabar 785630, Assam, India

TTB15-1 is a medium-duration variety suitable for transplanted ahu (autumn) season in Assam under rainfed conditions. The variety was developed at RARS from IR24/CR44-118-1 and has been recommended for cultivation in relatively flood-free medium-altitude ricelands.

Grain yield and duration of TTB15-1 in trials in Assam, India, 1984-88.

Year	Location	Growing condition	TTB15-1		Check			
			Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Designation	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Increase over check (%)
1984	Titabar	Ahu	4.3	115	Ch 63	3.8	111	15
1984	Titabar	Ahu	3.6	123	TTB2-6-1-1	3.2	134	14
1985	Karimganj	Ahu	2.2	116	IR50	1.9	111	17
1986	Karimganj	Ahu	2.8	114	IR50	2.2	103	32
1987	Karimganj	Ahu	2.8	118	IR50	2.6	111	8
1987	Titabar	Ahu	2.9	124	TTB2-6-1-1	2.4	132	20
1987	Titabar	Sali	4.0	124	Ratna	2.9	116	34
1988	Titabar	Ahu	5.5	125	Ratna	4.0	128	37
	Mean		3.5	120		2.9		23
<i>On-farm trial</i>								
1986	Gelapukhuri	Ahu	2.7	125	Takuguni	1.4	117	97
1988	Gelapukhuri	Ahu	4.2	123	Takuguni	1.9	114	125